

A PARADIGM SHIFT FROM TRADITIONAL TO MODERN EDUCATION - A TRANS EFFECT ON STUDENTS IN THANE DISTRICT

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Abstract :

The most common criticism about India's current educational system is that it does not lead to a meaningful employment. Even a perfect score of 90% may not ensure a good career in the near future. Ironically, for the past 34 years, our educational system has been entirely centred on grades, with a heavy emphasis on various types of traditional evaluations and tests. The new National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 will succeed the current National Policy on Education, which was initially created in 1986 and last revised in 1992. In order to study A Paradigm Shifts from Traditional to Modern Education; this study was conducted on students who residing in the Thane District. The study consists of primary and secondary data. A structured questionnaire was used for data collection with 5-points Likert scale. Null hypotheses were tested using Kruskal Wallis test. This study will raise student awareness and assist them to understand the effects of NEP on their lives and also beneficial to Teachers, Institutions and Government for the effective execution of NEP.

Key words: *National Education Policy, Paradigm Shift, Traditional to Modern Education*

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Introduction :

NEP is the first comprehensive, interactive, and holistic approach to reforming the educational system. This new education strategy for 2020 considers a variety of factors, including personal experiences, empirical research, stakeholder feedback, and lessons learned from best approaches. It is a positive move, and if executed correctly, this new educational framework can bring India up to pace with the world's leading nations. Changes in the educational system will have an impact on everyone from kids to parents to instructors.

NEP 2020 will provide students with additional learning options. The most significant effect would be a shift in the learning environment and process for students. The new education policy will:

- Place a greater emphasis on students' skill development and competency development.
- Develop 21st-century abilities in pupils to prepare them for the future.
- Encourage pupils to pursue both academic and non-academic goals.
- Provide pre-primary, open, and distance-learning students with a variety of learning possibilities.
- Provide students with access to counselling and other resources.

Therefore, this new national education strategy, mid-term drop-out students with 1 year of training or 2 years of diploma will have several departure possibilities. As a result of so many developing possibilities, students' interest and confusion will grow. It is recommended that individuals seek the advice of experts and professionals while making career selections. The Teacher is the first expert the pupils encounter. As a result, the Indian government has something to give teachers.

Review of Literature :

Ajay Kurien (2020), focused on The influence of the NEP 2020 on Higher Education. This study also discussed the key aspects of NEP and how they impact the current educational system. It was also proposed that in order to adapt to quickly developing transmutations and disruptions, more evidence-based decision-making is required. NEP has made provision for real-time assessment methods as well as a participatory monitoring and review structure, which is comforting.

Dr. Rupesh G. Sawant (2020), focused on The impact of NEP 2020 on higher education. The essential components of NEP were also explored in this study, as well as how they affect the existing educational system. It was also suggested that more evidence-based decision-making be used in order to respond to rapidly evolving transmutations and disruptions. It's encouraging that the NEP includes real-time evaluation mechanisms as well as a participatory monitoring and review system.

Mridul Madhav Panditrao (2020), stated that the key aspects of the concerns, principles, goals, vision, challenges, and solutions. Higher education and its implementation have been the major focus. Other concerns such as vocational education, research, and online and digital education, to name a few, have also been given due consideration. Overall, the government has taken a noteworthy and extremely significant step forward. Only time will tell how much net effective output has been achieved.

Objectives :

1. To study and understand the concept of NEP in general and transdisciplinary in particular.
2. To analyse the level of awareness of students towards NEP, 2020.
3. To analyse trans-effect on students towards paradigm shift in Education.

Hypothesis :

H_0 : There is no significant difference between Stream and Awareness towards National Education Policy

H_1 : There is significant difference between Stream and Awareness towards National Education Policy

H_0 : There is no significant difference between Year of Study and Awareness towards National Education Policy

H_1 : There is significant difference between Year of Study and Awareness towards National Education Policy

H_0 : There is no significant difference between Stream and Effect on Students due to National Education Policy

H_1 : There is significant difference between Stream and Effect on Students due to National Education Policy

H_0 : There is no significant difference between Year of Study and Effect on Students related to National Education Policy

H_1 : There is significant difference between Year of Study and Effect on Students due to National Education Policy

H_0 : There is no significant relationship between Awareness of National Education Policy and its effects on Students.

H_1 : There is significant relationship between Awareness of National Education Policy and its effects on Students.

Research Methodology :

The research study is indicative and analytical in nature. Both primary and secondary data was collected. Primary data was collected by floating structured questionnaire through google form among Students in Thane District. The questionnaire was framed with five-point Likert scale. The secondary data was collected from books, articles & Research Paper and websites. The population for the study was Students in Thane District. The convenient Sampling Method was used. The questionnaire was subject to editing. Incomplete questionnaires were removed and complete questionnaires were taken into consideration. It gets classified, tabulated and summarized in the flow of paper. Normality Test was done & as the data was Non normal, Non Parametric test were applied.

Limitations of Study :

1. The area is restricted to Thane District.
2. Time constraint to meet more Students in Thane District

Data Analysis :

The data analysis was done by using SPSS package. The normality test was conducted to check normality of data by using Kolmogorov-Smirnov & Shapiro-Wilk test. The data was found to be Non Normal therefore null hypotheses were tested by using Non parametric tests i.e Kruskal Wallis test.

Normality Testing :

Normality was conducted for the data using Kolmogorov-Smirnov & Shapiro-Wilk test.

H_0 : Distribution is Normal

H_1 : Distribution is Non-Normal

Table 1 : Normality Test – Awareness and Effect on Students

	Kolmogorov-Smimov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Awareness	.234	162	.000	.837	162	.000
Effect	.154	162	.000	.843	162	.000

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Source: Primary data

The Table number 1 indicated that significant value was less than 0.05 which means null hypothesis is rejected that means Distribution is Non Normal hence appropriate Non Parametric test were used for further analysis.

Testing of Null Hypotheses :

H_0 : There is no significant difference between Stream and Awareness towards National Education Policy

H_1 : There is significant difference between Stream and Awareness towards National Education Policy

Table 2 : Kruskal Wallis Test- Stream and Awareness towards National Education Policy

Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision
There is no significant difference between Stream and Awareness towards National Education Policy	Independent-Samples Kruskal Wallis Test	.000	Reject the null hypothesis.

Source: Primary data

The Table number 2 indicated that the significant value is 0.000 which is lesser than 0.05 which means the Null Hypothesis is Rejected that means There is significant difference between Stream and Awareness towards National Education Policy

H_0 : There is no significant difference between Year of Study and Awareness towards National Education Policy

H_1 : There is significant difference between Year of Study and Awareness towards National Education Policy

Table 3 : Kruskal Wallis Test- Year and Awareness towards National Education Policy

Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision
There is no significant difference between Year of Study and Awareness towards National Education Policy	Independent-Samples Kruskal Wallis Test	.908	Retain the null hypothesis.

Source: Primary data

The Table number 3 indicated that the significant value is 0.908 which is greater than 0.05 which means the Null Hypothesis is Accepted that means There is no significant difference between Year of Study and Awareness towards National Education Policy.

H_0 : There is no significant difference between Stream and Effect on Students due to National Education Policy

H_1 : There is significant difference between Stream and Effect on Students due to National Education Policy

Table 4 : Kruskal Wallis Test- Stream and Effect on Students due to National Education Policy

Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision
There is no significant difference between Stream and Effect on Students due to National Education Policy	Independent-Samples Kruskal Wallis Test	.000	Reject the null hypothesis.

Source: Primary data

The Table number 4 indicated that the significant value is 0.000 which is lesser than 0.05 which means the Null Hypothesis is Rejected that means there is significant difference between Stream and Effect on Students due to National Education Policy.

H_0 : There is no significant difference between Year of Study and Effect on Students related to National Education Policy

H_1 : There is significant difference between Year of Study and Effect on Students due to National Education Policy

Table 5 : Kruskal Wallis Test- Year and Effect on Students due to National Education Policy

Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision
There is no significant difference between Year of Study and Effect on Students due to National Education Policy	Independent-Samples Kruskal Wallis Test	.962	Retain the null hypothesis.

Source: Primary data

The Table number 5 indicated that the significant value is 0.962 which is greater than 0.05 which means the Null Hypothesis is Accepted that means There is no significant difference between Year of Study and Effect on Students due to National Education Policy.

H_0 : There is no significant relationship between Awareness of National Education Policy and its effects on Students.

H_1 : There is significant relationship between Awareness of National Education Policy and its effects on Students.

Table 6 : Correlations between Awareness towards NEP & Effect of NEP on students

		Awareness towards NEP	Effect of NEP
Awareness	Pearson Correlation	1	.582**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	162	162
Effect	Pearson Correlation	.582**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	162	162

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The Table number 5 indicated that significant value is 0.000 which is less than 0.05 which means the Null Hypothesis is rejected that means there is significant relationship between Awareness of National Education Policy and its effects on Students. There is a strong positive Correlation between Awareness of National Education Policy and its effects on Students.

Findings :

- 18.5% students were form Arts stream, 41.4% from Commerce Stream, 40.1% from Science stream.
- 34.6% students were from 1st year, 32.7% from 2nd year, and 32.7% from 3rd year.
- It was found that irrespective of Year of Study, Awareness towards National Education Policy, Effect on students was same.
- From the Review of Literature, it was found that The emphasis was on higher education and its implementation. Other topics have been addressed, including vocational education, research, and online and digital education, to mention a few. Overall, the administration has taken a substantial and remarkable stride forward.
- There was a positive correlation between awareness towards NEP, 2020 and effects of students. There was a strong positive correlation which indicates that high awareness leads to high effects on students. So this is important to quote that there is correlation between Awareness and Effects.

Suggestions :

- Encouraging collaboration programmes amongst universities in the same city or area is one strategy to provide authentic multidisciplinary experiences for students. Regular sessions might be held online to save time on travel, but physical interaction can also be arranged on a regular basis to enhance reciprocal learning (Post-Covid).

2. To enhance self-sufficiency after the age of 18, students should be encouraged to develop skills in their chosen field and engage in some form of economic/productive activity, reducing their reliance on their parents. This is accomplished through vocational training and the development of their confidence in order to participate in earn-while-learn programmes.
3. In addition to core subjects, non-core topics, and optional subjects, the undergraduate programme should be constructed so that there are two skill-based subjects concentrating on employability skills and entrepreneur ability skills, respectively. Continuous internal assessment, rather than semester-end exams, should be used to assess these skill-based disciplines. Such an innovative strategy encourages students to pursue a career as an entrepreneur.
4. College/ School authorities should arrange workshop for the students to create more awareness about national education system reforms. They should also Organizing student programmes and assisting them in selecting several disciplines from which to pick, as well as identifying their abilities.
5. The college should provide digital library, various books, journals, newspapers, digital lab for the students and this will help them to develop their critical thinking skills as well as research skills.

Significance of Study :

Education Minister of India has described NEP 2020 as a visionary education policy of the twenty-first century through which India is harnessing the potential of every student in the country, universalizing education, building capacity, and transforming the learning landscape in order to create a new India and youth ready for the future. The present study significant to the students as they will be made more aware of the National Education Policy, 2020, and its effect. This would in turn generate various options that were available to the students and multidisciplinary education has to be very beneficial for them. The study is also beneficial to the Teachers to understand students and Government as it will help them to plan their future amendments.

Conclusion :

Every country's economy, social standing, technological adoption, and healthy human behaviour are all influenced by higher education. The education department of the country government is responsible for improving GER so that every person of the country has access to higher education opportunities. The National Education Policy of India 2020 is working toward this goal by enacting innovative policies to improve the quality, attractiveness, affordability, and supply of higher education by opening it up to the private sector while maintaining strict quality controls in every higher education institution. NEP-2020 is expected to achieve its goals by 2030 by encouraging merit-based admissions with free-ships and scholarships and merit. The higher education system will become more student-centred, allowing students to pick core and associated studies within and across fields. These alterations will begin in the academic year 2023-24 and will last until 2030, when the first degree of change is expected to be noticeable. As a result, the Indian higher education system is shifting from a teacher-centred to a student-centred approach, from information to knowledge, from marks to skills, from examinations to experiments, from learning to research, and from choice to competency.

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